

The interest rate policy causes inflation

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Abstract

We show that under current monetary operation arrangements, in a single currency region, the policy rate set by the central bank directly causes inflation, by definition. If the policy rate increases, the inflation rate moves upwards. If the policy rate is kept constant, the inflation rate is constant. But this *inflation rate* is never measured, it is an unobservable. We do however have very rough proxies for inflation, like the CPI — if we lag the potential causes of inflation then we have a causal model, but it is highly inexact, since the future measured CPI is not precisely the rate of change of the price level *faced by consumers today*, because the CPI will include all sorts of other dynamical effects over the intervening period. With such an inexact model, we construct and then test robustness of a causal graph based on modern-money assumptions, using available FRED time series. The logic that the interest rate causes inflation remains robust, up to the above qualifications.

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1 Introduction

We want to test a model for inflation inspired by Modern Money Theory (MMT). The idea is that the CB (central bank) policy rate is *by identity* from definitions the base floor inflation rate. The causal model for this is very easily motivated, because it is institutional, that is, it is obvious in policy statements and policy institution & enforcement actions. “Animal spirits” may be involved, but they are clearly documented on paper or electronic meeting records.

In the motivations §1.1 we show logically that the base interest rate equals the base inflation rate. This is however an untestable tautology, because no one can possibly measure the rate of change in prices faced by consumers today. The future CPI is not this quantity, it includes numerous other causes and actual animal spirits, and supply constraint effects.

This paper seeks to capture the next best result, which is the question of whether the future CPI can nonetheless “see” the logical tautology?

In prior scholarship Werner reached companion conclusions based on a weaker but more normative causal statistical analysis (using GARCH). [1, 2] Werner concluded: “[lower] interest rates are not negatively correlated with economic growth and do not cause growth.”

1.1 Motivations

We will define an *MMT System* as any single currency region where government (or a coalition, or an authority) is the currency monopolist, hence price-setter, not price-taker [3]. Most countries today are MMT systems, by this definition. However, the consequences for policy options that could be made available (even if just for debate) have not been fully explored in macroeconomics literature or parliaments (in our opinion).

One possible policy option is to set a permanent zero interest rate floor, and allow commercial banks to operate a competitive spread rate. This way the government takes its foot off the proverbial accelerator of supplying the economy with free basic income (only for people who have savings) in the form of long-term Treasury bonds.

As a simple point of logic, if there is no significant difference in propensity of savers to borrow and borrowers to save, then the currency monopoly offering a positive interest rate on bonds is pro-inflationary, through several channels, including,

- the own-price of the currency (the interest rate),
- forward prices (deliverable contracts),
- and the aforementioned interest-income channel (all demand for zero supply).

One should thus observe a causal influence of positive interest rate policy on forwards-inflation (the rate of change of the price level faced by consumers today).

This paper reports on an exploratory model for testing that logic with data analysis, intended to inform future research on causes of inflation that have previously been neglected. We should also emphasize that in MMT systems (government being the currency monopolist) it is a point of logic that the government floor policy interest rate sets the own-price and the forward price, and more-over provides the interest-income to support those upward price adjustments. But this need not apply to all prices in relative terms. A change in interest rates can cause one-time adjustments in prices either up or down, but relative prices are not our concern, and those narratives do not invalidate the logical point.

Note that the logic holds regardless of the data analysis:

Increasing the interest rate will cause an increase in the rate of change of the price level.

Yet we might over any given period *not* observe analytically a significant causal effect of pro-interest rate policy on the increase in the price level if there are more powerful causal factors at work.

Note our hypothesis is not a claim about measured *core* CPI inflation. *Core inflation* is an empirical index-number construct, usually designed to remove selected volatile components from a measured price index. The present identity claim concerns the institutional price of the currency itself.

The identity is not directly testable as an index-number proposition, because no one can measure the instantaneous rate of change of the general price level faced by consumers today. Future CPI is not this quantity. It is a constructed proxy affected by many other causes, including relative price movements, supply constraints, index methodology, expectations, and genuine market psychology.

This paper therefore asks the next-best empirical question: can future CPI nevertheless “see” the monetary-floor logic? That is, after controlling for the policy reaction function and selected confounders, is there a detectable positive causal signal from the policy rate to forward measured inflation?

Our study is first-order in the sense of looking at only the two rates: the own-price and the rate of change of the price level; as well as taking a basic data set. This leaves a lot of scope for variants of our study. One that should be particularly important to follow-up is how the *rate of change* of the interest rate $\Delta i/\Delta t$, (an accelerator) effects the forwards inflation rate and changes in relative prices of *different types* of commodity or asset, that have implications for socioeconomic *inequality*.

1.2 Outline of the Study

In this paper we limit our scope as follows:

1. We are only interested in two models, a simple base case causal model, and one extension to include an economic feedstock commodity (oil).
2. We are only going to analyse the MMT causation pathways.
3. Only one data set is used, the data available for the USA from the St Louis FED.

In causal relation analysis the main source of modelling disagreement can arise from the subjective expert's choice of causal diagram. It is therefore important to emphasize that no single causal model can be taken as definitive policy advice for decision makers. In choosing to analyse an MMT model for the impact of the policy rate on inflation we are excluding other expert subjective opinions and doctrines.

It is a separate matter to devise predictive models for testing a causal model. We will not be developing any prediction software in this paper. We encourage others to do so, so that competing macroeconomic paradigms can be compared (those whose domain experts would draw different causal diagrams).

1.3 The causal framework — a simple example

Consider the outcome Y = movement in the inflation rate, π . It is important for our analysis this is the forward rate, not the backwards CPI or other proxy, because we want to conduct a causal inference analysis. We will thus be examining lagged responses.

Our treatment variable X is the policy rate, x .

The conditional expectation value,

$$E(Y|X = x) \tag{1}$$

can be observed. It measures among the observed units whose treatment variable naturally took value x , the average value of Y .

The causal quantity of interest is different, and is denoted by the causal expectation value,

$$E(Y|do(X = x)) \tag{2}$$

which means: if we intervene on the system and set $X = x$ for the relevant population, what would the average value of Y be?

The first (1) is observational conditioning, and expresses merely a statistical association. The variable X could have equally been the cause of a change in Y . Or any number of confounding variables may have been responsible for most of the variation or trend in Y .

The second (2) is an interventional expectation. Pearl [4] introduced the $do(\cdot)$ notation precisely to distinguish “seeing” $X = x$ from “setting” $X = x$. In Pearl's formulation, $P(Y = y | do(X = x))$ denotes the probability that $Y = y$ would occur if the treatment condition $X = x$ were enforced uniformly over the population.

The difference matters because the observed group with $X = x$ may be systematically different from the group with $X \neq x$. In a DAG (directed acyclic graph) model, this usually means there is some confounder Z . In a DAG (directed acyclic graph), this is represented by the confounding fork

where Z is a common cause of both X and Y . Then

$$E(Y | X = x)$$

mixes the causal effect of X on Y with the selection effect caused by Z . But

$$E(Y \mid do(X = x))$$

cuts the natural causes of X . Graphically, the intervention deletes incoming arrows into X . Any arrows going into X are potential paths to Y that are termed *backdoor paths*. If the original structural equation was

$$X = f_X(Z, U_X),$$

then the intervention replaces it with

$$X := x.$$

In the case of interest rate policy, the intervention does not ask, “what happens among economies that happen to have high interest rates?” It asks,

What happens if the policy authority sets the interest rate high, holding the rest of the structural model intact except for the mechanism that normally determines the interest rate?

For our interest-rate question, this distinction is central. The observational quantity

$$E(\pi \mid i = 8\%)$$

asks: what inflation do we observe in countries/periods where the central bank (CB) interest rate is 8%? But high interest rates are usually chosen when inflation is already high, expected to rise, or politically salient. So $E(\pi \mid i = 8\%)$ may be high even if raising rates lowers inflation, raises inflation, or has little effect. It is contaminated by the policy-reaction function.

The causal quantity is instead

$$E(\pi \mid do(i = 8\%))$$

which asks: what would inflation be if the policy rate were set to 8% by intervention, rather than taking the value generated by the central bank’s usual reaction function?

Let, D = aggregate demand pressure, π^e = expected inflation, i = policy interest rate, π = realized inflation.

A minimal DAG for the policy-rate/inflation question is then

Here D and π^e are confounders: each is a common cause of the policy rate i and realized inflation π . Therefore the observational association

$$E(\pi \mid i)$$

does not, by itself, identify the causal effect

$$E(\pi \mid do(i)).$$

In such a graph, the raw association $E(\pi \mid i)$ is not the causal effect of i on π , because i is partly a response to inflationary conditions.

1.4 Example of unemployment

Another example we will study in a separate paper might be the cause of unemployment. There are many associations, but few credible causal models. In particular, the NAIRU framework has proven to be completely false, and was never even merely associational, let alone causal in any way.

For our unemployment hypothesis, the same distinction applies. The observational statement

$$E(u \mid \tau > 0)$$

where τ denotes tax liability, is not automatically the causal effect of taxation on unemployment. The causal claim would be closer to

$$E(u \mid do(\tau > 0))$$

or more precisely a structural intervention such as

do(state imposes non-dischargeable tax liabilities payable only in state currency).

That is not a simple scalar treatment like a medical drug. It is an institutional intervention. So the DAG will probably need variables such as tax liability, currency monopolist spending policy, public employment offer, private-sector demand, wage floor, fiscal balance, desired net saving, and involuntary unemployment.

An important methodological point is this: a verified DAG does not prove the MMT hypotheses in these study cases. It forces us to state exactly which arrows we believe exist, which arrows are absent, which variables confound which relationships, and which estimand corresponds to the claim. For this This makes the MMT framework empirically contestable rather than merely rhetorical.

We mention this example partly because in our final model for inflation and interest rates, we will include unemployment and taxation as causal factors influencing π . (See §2.) But more importantly, our companion study — in a separate paper — on the *causes of unemployment* is far more critical, and implicates moral reasoning and potential crimes against humanity. The present study is a more sedate and academic exercise with less emotional risk for policy makers paying heed to our research.

1.5 Methodology

Our methodology has three stages. First, we formulate the causal hypothesis as a structural model. Second, we test the software and the logic of the estimators on simulated data, where the true causal structure is known by construction. Third, we apply the same workflow to empirical macroeconomic time series, using public data such as the Federal Reserve Economic Data database (FRED).

The first stage is conceptual. We begin by specifying a DAG for the hypothesised causal structure. The DAG records which variables are treated as causes of other variables, which variables are possible confounders, and which intervention is being studied. In the interest-rate model, the principal treatment variable is the policy interest rate i_t , and the principal outcome variable is future realized inflation π_{t+1} . The causal estimand is therefore of the form

$$E(\pi_{t+1} \mid do(i_t = i)).$$

This estimand is distinct from the observational conditional expectation

$$E(\pi_{t+1} \mid i_t = i),$$

because the policy rate is not randomly assigned. It is chosen by a central bank in response to past inflation, expected inflation, unemployment, financial conditions, political constraints, and the prevailing economic doctrine of the policy committee. A causal design must therefore model the policy reaction function well enough to distinguish the consequences of setting i_t from the circumstances under which i_t was in fact chosen.

The DAG is then used to identify admissible adjustment sets. If a variable is a common cause of i_t and π_{t+1} , then failing to adjust for it will generally bias the estimated

effect of the policy rate. Conversely, adjusting for a collider, a descendant of the treatment, or a variable lying on the causal pathway may introduce bias rather than remove it. The DAG is not decorative in other words, it determines which conditional distributions are legitimate targets for estimation and which regressions are causally misleading.

The second stage uses simulated data. We construct artificial economies from known structural equations. In these simulations, the data-generating process is chosen by us, so the true causal effect is known. This allows us to verify that the software recovers the correct effect in cases where the identification assumptions are satisfied, and fails in the expected way when those assumptions are violated. For example, we can simulate a policy reaction function in which the central bank raises i_t in response to expected inflation π_t^e , while π_t^e also affects future realized inflation π_{t+1} . In such a simulation, the raw association between i_t and π_{t+1} need not equal the causal effect of i_t on π_{t+1} . The simulated data therefore provide a controlled environment for demonstrating why $E(\pi_{t+1} | i_t = i)$ and $E(\pi_{t+1} | do(i_t = i))$ are different quantities.

The simulation stage also lets us test rival causal stories. We can generate data from a model in which higher interest rates reduce inflation, from a model in which higher interest rates increase inflation through cost-of-capital and income-channel effects, and from a model in which the direct effect of interest rates on employment is weak. We can then ask whether the estimation procedure correctly distinguishes these cases when the relevant confounders are observed, when some are omitted, and when the functional form is misspecified. This stage is therefore a validation of the computational workflow, not yet a test of the real economy.

The third stage applies the validated workflow to empirical data. The empirical model replaces theoretical variables by measured time-series proxies. For example, i_t may be represented by a policy-rate series, π_{t+1} by a measured inflation series, $U_{r,t-k:t}$ by recent unemployment-rate observations, and D_t by either a latent factor or a vector of observed macroeconomic controls. The effective tax variable T_t is more difficult, because the theoretical claim concerns tax liability as an institutional constraint, whereas the available data are usually tax receipts, average tax rates, statutory rates, or constructed effective rates. The empirical section must therefore distinguish the theoretical node T_t from any particular measured proxy for it.

Because macroeconomic time series are temporal, the empirical DAG must also respect timing. Policy decisions at time t cannot be caused by inflation at time $t + 1$, although they may be caused by past inflation, published forecasts, and expected future inflation. The empirical model will therefore use lagged information sets. Schematically, the central-bank reaction function is modelled as depending on information available at the time of the decision,

$$i_t = f_i(\pi_{t-k:t}, \pi_t^e, U_{r,t-k:t}, D_t, \dots, \varepsilon_t^i),$$

while realized future inflation is modelled as

$$\pi_{t+1} = f_\pi(i_t, \pi_t^e, D_t, \dots, \varepsilon_{t+1}^\pi).$$

These equations are not introduced as final parametric assumptions. They state the temporal logic of the causal model: the policy rate is a decision made from currently available information, while the outcome is measured after that decision.

We will compare the raw observational association between i_t and π_{t+1} with adjusted estimates motivated by the DAG. We will examine whether the sign and magnitude of the estimated effect are stable under alternative proxy choices, lag structures, and rival DAG specifications. We will not treat a single regression coefficient as decisive. The purpose is to determine whether the evidence is more consistent with the conventional claim that higher interest rates suppress inflation, the MMT-frame claim that higher interest rates may contribute to inflation through income and cost channels, or a weak-effect claim in which policy-rate changes are largely reactive rather than strongly causal.

This methodology also clarifies the role of the paper. The aim is not to produce a central-bank forecasting model. The aim is to make a causal hypothesis explicit, build

software that can distinguish interventional effects from observational associations in controlled examples, and then apply the same discipline to real macroeconomic data. The result should be understood as a causal-model comparison rather than as a claim that one DAG has exhausted the structure of the economy.

This ends our overview of the basic framework. We now turn to the actual full model we will be analysing.

2 The Base Case Model — MMT-I

Macroeconomics is a complicated subject, but it is driven by human decisions, not just biochemical impulses. The causal relations are therefore often far easier to ascertain than in a field like population biology for example. We know exactly the cause of a floor interest rate change: the vote at the central bank boards of governors. They do not get to vote on the rate of inflation. So π is our target.

One may consume past published FED Committee minutes to get a good idea of what factors go into the CB reaction function. Our objective is to make a rough model for the reaction function, not to develop a highly predictive model. (We leave that to future researchers.) We do not aim to make any predictions either, our study is purely conceptual, and designed to educate policy-makers. That stated, it should be possible for policy-makers to use our results to commission analysts to build predictive models and scenario tests, to supplement whatever existing methods the governing institutions are using.

The past rate of inflation is what contributes to the CB vote, not the future rate. But there is a third issue which is the psychological or theoretical expected future rate.

We add unemployment as both a policy-reaction input and a macro-state variable affected by taxation. We do not yet put U_r in as a direct cause of π , because we do not accept a Phillips-curve channel. Since this is an MMT-frame model, it is important to begin by *not* assuming that unemployment mechanically disciplines inflation. That can later be added as a rival DAG.

For the DAG, use a base case. Let

1. D_t = aggregate demand pressure at time t ,
2. π_t^e = expected inflation at time t ,
3. $U_{r,t-k:t}$ = recent unemployment-rate history observed by the central bank,
4. T_t = effective aggregate tax rate or tax-liability intensity at time t ,
5. i_t = policy interest rate at time t ,
6. π_{t+1} = realized inflation in the next period.

Here $U_{r,t-k:t}$ denotes the recent unemployment information available to the central bank at the time of the policy-rate decision. The index range $t-k : t$ is meant to include the last few monthly or quarterly unemployment observations, depending on the data frequency used in the empirical model.

In this DAG, T_t is a cause of unemployment, represented by $T_t \rightarrow U_{r,t-k:t}$. The recent unemployment-rate history $U_{r,t-k:t}$ is then an input into the central-bank policy-rate decision, represented by $U_{r,t-k:t} \rightarrow i_t$. Aggregate demand pressure D_t and expected inflation π_t^e are also inputs into the policy decision, and they are also direct causes of

realized inflation. The policy rate i_t is allowed to have a direct causal effect on realized inflation, which is precisely the effect whose sign and magnitude we wish to estimate.

The corresponding causal estimand is

$$E(\pi_{t+1} \mid do(i_t = i)).$$

The observational conditional expectation

$$E(\pi_{t+1} \mid i_t = i)$$

does not generally identify this quantity, because i_t is chosen partly in response to macroeconomic conditions. In the graph above, those conditions include D_t , π_t^e , and $U_{r,t-k:t}$.

The node D_t should not be interpreted as a directly observed scalar. It denotes a *latent macroeconomic state*: the pressure of current nominal spending and real activity relative to the economy's current productive, logistical, and institutional capacity. In empirical work, D_t must be operationalized by one or more observed proxies, such as an output gap, capacity utilization, real activity indexes, nominal-income growth, or a vector of macroeconomic controls. Because some common indexes already include unemployment, the empirical definition of D_t must be chosen so that it does not merely reintroduce $U_{r,t-k:t}$ under another name.

The theoretical DAG contains the latent macroeconomic state D_t . The empirical design replaces D_t by a measured proxy vector M_t . This distinction matters because the causal graph concerns structural relations, while the empirical dataset contains only measured indicators.

Status of the DAG.

The DAG is not a claim to have drawn causal reality. It is a modelling choice. The investigator chooses a graph in order to make a causal hypothesis explicit: which arrows are asserted, which arrows are excluded, which variables are treated as confounders, and which intervention is being studied. This is especially important in economics, where social behaviour, legal institutions, expectations, accounting conventions, and policy doctrines interact. A causal model in this setting is therefore not an essentialist description of an economic object. It is a disciplined way of making a theoretical claim testable.

This point is not merely philosophical. Economic paradigms can themselves become causal forces. A false theory of inflation, unemployment, or public finance may drastically influence central-bank votes, fiscal rules, wage bargaining, investment decisions, and public expectations. Hence a DAG may need to include not only material variables, such as taxes, unemployment, interest rates, and prices, but also institutional beliefs and policy reaction functions. For this reason, competing DAGs should be constructed, contrasted and compared. The purpose of the base-case DAG is to state the MMT-frame hypothesis clearly, not to prevent rival graphs from being analysed.

2.0.1 Synthetic-data validation

Before applying the model to empirical macroeconomic data, we first test the causal workflow on synthetic data. The purpose of this stage is not to simulate a realistic economy. The purpose is to construct a data-generating process in which the true causal effect is known. We can then check whether the estimation procedure recovers the known effect when the graph is correctly specified, and whether it fails in predictable ways when relevant confounders are omitted.

We use the following structural equations:

$$\begin{aligned} T_t &= \varepsilon_t^T, \\ D_t &= \varepsilon_t^D, \\ \pi_t^e &= a_D D_t + \varepsilon_t^e, \\ U_{r,t} &= b_T T_t + b_D D_t + \varepsilon_t^U, \end{aligned}$$

$$i_t = c_e \pi_t^e + c_D D_t + c_U U_{r,t} + \varepsilon_t^i,$$

$$\pi_{t+1} = \beta_{i \rightarrow \pi} i_t + d_e \pi_t^e + d_D D_t + \varepsilon_{t+1}^\pi.$$

The parameter $\beta_{i \rightarrow \pi}$ is the true direct causal effect of the policy rate on next-period inflation. Since the data-generating process is known, we can set $\beta_{i \rightarrow \pi} < 0$, $\beta_{i \rightarrow \pi} = 0$, or $\beta_{i \rightarrow \pi} > 0$, and verify that the causal estimator recovers the corresponding sign and magnitude.

The observational association between i_t and π_{t+1} is not expected to equal $\beta_{i \rightarrow \pi}$, because i_t is partly a policy response to variables that also affect π_{t+1} . In particular, D_t and π_t^e are common causes of i_t and π_{t+1} . The simulation gives a controlled demonstration of the distinction between

$$E(\pi_{t+1} \mid i_t = i)$$

and

$$E(\pi_{t+1} \mid do(i_t = i)).$$

The results of the validation exercise are summarized in Table 1. The purpose of the exercise is to check that the causal workflow distinguishes observational association from interventional effect when the true data-generating process is known.

Table 1: Synthetic-data validation of the causal estimator.

True effect $\beta_{i \rightarrow \pi}$	Naive OLS	Adjusted OLS	DAG-adjusted estimate
-0.2000	0.5294	-0.1971	-0.1970
0.0000	0.7294	0.0029	0.0030
0.2000	0.9294	0.2029	0.2030

The naïve OLS column is included as a diagnostic contrast: it estimates the unadjusted observational association, not the causal effect. Its bias is by a reaction function and is correlated with variables that also influence future inflation. The validation check is that the DAG-adjusted estimates recover the known structural effect. In Table 1, both adjusted OLS and the DoWhy estimate recover the negative, zero, and positive causal effects to simulation error.

The final column reports the causal estimate obtained from the specified DAG-adjusted identification procedure. In this example it is computed using the Python package `dowhy`, but the estimand is software-independent: the same adjustment implied by the same DAG can be implemented in R, Julia, or any other statistical environment.

You may also call the *DAG adjusted estimate* the *Backdoor adjusted estimate*.

* * *

At this point one could proceed to collect time series data and conduct the real world causal relation analysis. Before we do so, the Base Case needs to be extended. This is an important part of casual discovery: to vary the model and compare results across different models. In most sciences one must forego any claims to have found a one true model, and the social aspects of science come into play. The social discourse that informs policy analysis and decision making needs such subjective debate, precisely because metaphysical causality is impossible to determine. Relative importance of causal relations are not impossible to determine, provided they are given appropriate scope.

The latter means, among other things, within a broad class of similar models, conceived of by subjective appraisals, some might be distinguished as objectively better than others — given the same data set as input.

2.1 MMT-II extension: energy-input commodity pressure

The base-case DAG deliberately suppresses external commodity-price shocks. This is useful pedagogically, because it isolates the policy-rate reaction problem. However, a

more realistic macroeconomic model should include energy and feedstock costs. In the present world economy, fossil fuels remain a dominant energy input, so a crude-oil price series can serve as a first empirical proxy for this channel. We denote the Brent crude oil price by $O_{B,t}$.

The empirical motivation is straightforward: the world economy is still strongly fossil-fuel dependent. The IEA world energy-mix data¹ give oil and oil products, coal, and natural gas as the dominant components of total energy supply, with oil and oil products alone listed at about 30.2% of world total energy supply. The Energy Institute’s Statistical Review page reports that fossil fuels still account for about 86% of the energy mix under its current accounting approach. These numbers justify using oil as a first proxy for energy/feedstock commodity pressure, while also noting that the relevant commodity basket may change as solar, wind, hydro, geothermal, nuclear, battery, and grid infrastructure become more central.

The node $O_{B,t}$ should not be interpreted as the only possible commodity input into inflation. It is an ersatz measure for a wider energy and feedstock-cost channel. As energy systems change, the relevant empirical node may need to be replaced by a broader commodity basket, possibly including natural gas, electricity prices, grid inputs, battery minerals, uranium, construction materials, or other inputs relevant to solar, wind, hydro, geothermal, and nuclear production. [5–7] The purpose of the Level-II extension is to show how the base DAG can be enlarged when an omitted supply-side cost factor is judged causally important.

The Level-II, or MMT-II, DAG extends the base model by allowing $O_{B,t}$ to affect expected inflation, unemployment, aggregate demand pressure, and realized future inflation:

$$O_{B,t} \rightarrow \pi_t^e, \quad O_{B,t} \rightarrow U_{r,t-k:t}, \quad O_{B,t} \rightarrow D_t, \quad O_{B,t} \rightarrow \pi_{t+1}.$$

The resulting DAG is:

The Level-II simulation repeats the same validation check after adding the commodity-price node $O_{B,t}$. The structural equations now include arrows from $O_{B,t}$ into D_t , $U_{r,t-k:t}$, π_t^e , and π_{t+1} . The purpose of the exercise is to check that the estimator continues to recover the known direct effect of i_t on π_{t+1} when an external energy-input cost channel is included. As before, the naive OLS column is interpreted only as an observational contrast; the validation target is the *DAG-adjusted* estimate.

A even more realistic model might include other real production feedstocks independent of oil and thus carrying additional supply shock or boom information. One can of course “go to town” with a causal model, including arrows for anything one can measure. Our compute power was limited so we will document the simpler analysis, with oil as an ersatz for commodity supply booms and shocks.

¹See <https://www.iea.org/world/energy-mix> and the Energy Institute data here: <https://www.energyinst.org/statistical-review>, and the IEEj Report <https://enenken.ieej.or.jp/data/12598.pdf>.

2.2 Model Options

We’ve already discussed the scientific protocol issue with Causal models like our DAG’s: they are subjective, and choices are driven by experts with domain knowledge, and are open to debate.

One such freedom of modellers for time series data like our case is to lag other factors, not just the target inflation rate, $\pi_{t+\delta}$. For the present purposes, which are to illustrate an MMT analysis of interest rate policy, we have chosen not to run such scenarios, partly due to lack of resources. We do intend to run more detailed analysis in the future funding permitting.

The main option is of course an entirely different causal diagram. We also do not consider this option because the scope of the present paper is limited to presenting the MMT scenario. Competing macroeconomics paradigms are not our concern in this particular study. But hopefully other research groups will pick up this slack, because it is of enormous importance to inform policy makers — who may not have expertise in monetary operations — of options they have available that past economic doctrine had failed to supply at the higher political levels. This includes informing public opinion.

2.3 Model analysis specifics

Under-the-hood, the type of causal analysis our model performs has a specific flow:

specify a causal graph \rightarrow identify the estimand, \rightarrow estimate the identified effect \rightarrow and optionally run refutation/robustness checks.

In our use case the graph encodes the causal assumptions, and the backdoor linear-regression estimator gives a slope-like average causal effect for a continuous treatment.

3 Empirical Data

The FRED series² we used were as follows:

FEDFUNDS for the effective federal funds rate.,

CPIAUCSL for CPI.

UNRATE for unemployment.

MICH for one-year Michigan inflation expectations.

CFNAI for aggregate activity/demand-pressure proxy.

W006RC1Q027SBEA plus GDP to construct a quarterly federal tax-receipts-to-GDP proxy.

DCOILBRENTTEU for Brent crude oil.

The FRED describe *FEDFUNDS* as the effective federal funds rate, *UNRATE* as U-3 unemployment, *MICH* as median expected price change over the next 12 months, *CFNAI* as an index of overall economic activity and related inflationary pressure, *DCOILBRENTTEU* as daily Brent crude prices, and GDP as gross domestic product.

For the tax proxy, *W006RC1Q027SBEA* is federal government current tax receipts. Dividing it by nominal GDP gives a rough federal tax-receipts share of GDP. That is not yet the full theoretical T_t node, but it is a transparent first empirical proxy.

4 Comparison of the Two Models

We begin with a default ‘first’ analysis in §4.1 including a lag analysis.

4.1 A First analysis

The empirical analysis treats the forward inflation horizon as a modelling choice. Instead of fixing the outcome as π_{t+1} , we define

$$\pi_{t+h}$$

²From <https://fred.stlouisfed.org/>.

to be realized year-over-year CPI inflation $\delta = h$ months after the policy-rate observation. The causal estimand is therefore

$$E(\pi_{t+h} \mid do(i_t = i)).$$

We scan a pre-specified finite grid of horizons,

$$h \in \{1, 2, \dots, 18\},$$

and report the estimated arrow strength $i_t \rightarrow \pi_{t+h}$ across the full grid. The reported selected horizon is the horizon with the largest absolute DAG-adjusted estimate on that grid. This is an exploratory selection rule, so the full lag curve is reported alongside the selected value. If the selected horizon lies at either boundary of the grid, the result is treated as a warning that the relevant lag may lie outside the tested range.

For each horizon h , the analysis constructs a dataset containing the treatment i_t , the outcome π_{t+h} , and the observed adjustment variables specified by the DAG. The causal graph is then passed to the estimation routine, which first identifies the backdoor-adjusted estimand and then estimates the corresponding effect using a linear backdoor regression. The resulting coefficient is interpreted as the estimated average change in π_{t+h} associated with a one-unit intervention on i_t , conditional on the identifying assumptions encoded in the DAG.

The naive OLS estimate is also reported, but only as a diagnostic contrast. It is the unadjusted observational association between i_t and π_{t+h} . The DAG-adjusted estimate is the relevant estimate for the causal arrow in the specified model. Comparing the naive and adjusted columns therefore indicates how much of the raw association is attributable to the policy reaction function and the observed confounding structure.

4.1.1 Causal analysis outputs

In the MMT-II model, the Oil node is implemented empirically using a Brent crude oil proxy. The default specification uses the year-over-year log change in Brent crude,

$$\Delta_{12} \log O_{B,t} = 100(\log O_{B,t} - \log O_{B,t-12}),$$

rather than the raw price level. This reduces the risk that the estimate is driven by common low-frequency trends rather than by commodity-price pressure relevant to the inflation horizon.

The DAG specifies the causal structure and determines which variables must be adjusted for. Once this adjustment set is identified, the effect is estimated using a *linear backdoor regression*. For each horizon selected, h , the estimated equation has the schematic form

$$\pi_{t+h} = \alpha_h + \beta_h i_t + \Gamma_h^\top Z_t + \varepsilon_{t+h},$$

where Z_t denotes the DAG-implied adjustment set. The reported DAG-adjusted estimate in Table 2 is $\hat{\beta}_h$, the estimated coefficient on the policy rate i_t . (The coefficients reported in Tables below are these regression coefficients, *not* normalized weights on the arrows of the DAG.)

Thus $\hat{\beta}_h$ is interpreted as the estimated average change in forward year-over-year CPI inflation, measured in percentage points, associated with a one percentage point intervention on the policy rate, conditional on the identifying assumptions encoded in the DAG. For example, $\hat{\beta}_h = 0.17$ means that a one percentage point increase in the policy rate is estimated to increase π_{t+h} by approximately 0.17 percentage points at horizon h . This is a causal interpretation only within the specified DAG and estimator; it is not a normalized graph-theoretic arrow weight.

4.1.2 Empirical lag scan

Narrow Model Horizon.

The selected horizon is the horizon with the largest absolute DAG-adjusted estimate on this grid. This selection rule is exploratory, and we will refer to this model as the *Narrow Model*, since it lacks a commodity or real supply price input.

The full lag curve was inspected, because the selected horizon by itself can conceal whether the estimate is isolated, monotone, unstable, or located at the boundary of the search grid.

In the present run, both the MMT-I and MMT-II specifications select the lower boundary, $h = 1$. Selected scans are shown in Table 2.

In our code this triggers a boundary warning: the largest effect in the tested grid occurs at the shortest horizon considered. The warning does not invalidate the result, but it does mean that the one-month estimate should be read together with the full lag profile rather than as a uniquely identified structural delay.

The selected one-month horizon is not implausible for the inflation equation. The treatment variable is a central-bank policy-rate observation, and modern financial markets can adjust asset prices, exchange rates, wholesale funding costs, and mark-up expectations rapidly after a policy decision or policy signal. The model is therefore compatible with a short measured horizon for price-level and inflation-expectation channels. This does not imply that all macroeconomic responses are so rapid. Variables such as unemployment, investment, hiring, lay-offs, and household saving behaviour may respond over longer horizons. Those lags are important for a separate causal study of the effect of policy rates on employment or labour utilisation. The present analysis targets the causal arrow from the policy rate to forward inflation.

The lag scan also shows that the estimated effect declines as the horizon is extended. In both MMT-I and MMT-II, the DAG-adjusted estimate is largest at $h = 1$ and then falls gradually across the tested range. There is a mild flattening in the neighbourhood of $h = 12$, but this feature is small relative to the overall downward profile. The Level-II (+Oil) specification does not materially change the selected horizon or the sign of the estimate. This suggests that, under the present DAG and proxy choices, adding the Brent oil-price channel changes the estimated magnitude only slightly.

The substantive result of this exploratory scan is therefore that the estimated policy-rate arrow is positive over the tested horizons. At the selected one-month horizon, the DAG-adjusted estimate is approximately 0.171 in MMT-I and approximately 0.169 in MMT-II. Interpreted literally within the linear backdoor specification, this means that a one percentage point intervention on the policy rate is associated with an estimated increase of roughly 0.17 percentage points in forward year-over-year CPI inflation at the one-month horizon. This interpretation is conditional on the DAG, the measured proxy variables, the linear estimator, and the exploratory lag-selection rule.

Table 2: Selected empirical lag-scan results.

Model	Selected h	Naive OLS	Adjusted OLS	DAG-adjusted estimate
MMT-I	1	0.2439	0.1374	0.1713
MMT-II	1	0.2439	0.1458	0.1689

4.1.3 Discussions of narrow DAG results

Because the selected horizon is the lower boundary of the grid, the result should be treated as evidence for a short-horizon association within the specified causal model, not as proof that the true economic response is completed in one month. The boundary result motivates a robustness check using a shorter-frequency event-study design, if suitable high-frequency policy and price data are later introduced. With the present monthly FRED data, the one-month horizon is the shortest admissible forward horizon.

4.2 A Second Wider Analysis

The next step is to add inference and robustness around this lag scan. We extend the analysis to report confidence intervals or HAC standard errors in the markdown summary, run the refuters for the selected horizons, and rerun the MMT-II model with alternative oil specifications: $O_{B,t}$, $\log O_{B,t}$, and $\Delta_{12} \log O_{B,t}$. After that, we ran subsample checks, for example pre-2008, post-2008, and post-2020 excluded, because monetary policy regimes and inflation dynamics are not stationary over the full 1988–2026 sample.

We proceeded in this order:

1. rerun the lag scan with alternative oil definitions, especially O_B and $\log O_B$ versus $\Delta_{12} \log O_B$;
2. ran again with a wider grid, $h = 1, \dots, 36$ to see whether the decline continues;
3. added confidence intervals or HAC standard-error bands to the lag plot;
4. run DoWhy refuters for the selected horizons.
5. ran subsample checks, for example pre-2008, post-2008, and post-2020 excluded.

After this, we will report on our concluding remarks based on the results in §5, leaving further use of the methodology to other investigators.

4.2.1 Alternative oil definitions

The Level-II model contains an oil-price node, but the empirical implementation of this node is not unique. We therefore reran the MMT-II lag scan under three price transforms:

$$O_{B,t}, \quad \log O_{B,t}, \quad \Delta_{12} \log O_{B,t} = 100(\log O_{B,t} - \log O_{B,t-12}).$$

The first specification uses the Brent crude price level directly. The second uses the log price level. The third uses the year-over-year log change in Brent crude, which treats oil as a commodity-price pressure variable rather than as a low-frequency price-level series.

The purpose of this check is to determine whether the estimated policy-rate arrow is an artefact of a particular oil transformation. If the sign and selected horizon are stable across these three definitions, then the Level-II conclusion is not being driven by the arbitrary choice of oil-price scaling. If the estimates change sharply across definitions, then the oil node should be treated as a fragile part of the empirical specification.

The sensitivity results are summarized in Table 3. Each row reports the selected horizon under the same lag-selection rule used above, together with the naïve OLS, adjusted OLS, and DAG-adjusted estimates.

With our FRED data we still get a best horizon $h = 1$.

Table 3: MMT-II oil-definition sensitivity check.

Oil node	Selected h	Naïve OLS	Adjusted OLS	DAG-adjusted estimate
$O_{B,t}$	1	0.2439	0.1356	0.1374
$\log O_{B,t}$	1	0.2439	0.1177	0.1374
$\Delta_{12} \log O_{B,t}$	1	0.2439	0.1458	0.1689

These results report different empirical representations of the Level-II oil DAG node, so some numerical variation is expected. The robustness question is whether the qualitative conclusion changes: the sign of the estimated policy-rate arrow, the approximate magnitude of the selected-horizon effect, and the selected lag profile. Stability across these definitions supports the claim that the Level-II result is not an artefact of the oil-price transform adopted.

For the untransformed $O_{B,t}$ specification and the $\log O_{B,t}$ specification, the lag curves show a noticeable upward inflection near $h = 12$. However, the DAG-adjusted estimate at that horizon does not exceed the selected one-month estimate. In both cases the $h = 12$ estimate is approximately 0.137, while the largest estimate on the tested grid remains at $h = 1$.

Including the untransformed oil-price node attenuates the selected-horizon DAG-adjusted estimate from about 0.17 to about 0.14, a reduction of roughly 20%. This is consistent with the interpretation that oil prices absorb part of the supply-side inflation variation that the simpler model could otherwise attribute to the policy-rate channel. The result should be read as a robustness check rather than as a formal significance test: the estimated policy-rate arrow remains positive, but its magnitude is moderately reduced when an explicit oil-price channel is included.

4.2.2 Wider Grid Results

Given the trend in coefficient magnitude was downwards for increasing h , we only ran a wider grid out to $h = 36$ months, see Fig.1. A local maxima near $h = 12$ is again apparent and clearly that's the best horizon other than $h = 1$ that we have available.

The shaded bands in the lag plot, Fig.1, are approximate HAC/Newey–West confidence bands for the linear backdoor regression coefficient. The point estimate is the DAG-adjusted estimate for the arrow $i_t \rightarrow \pi_{t+h}$, while the band reflects serial-correlation-robust sampling uncertainty in the corresponding linear adjustment regression.

Fig. 1: Coefficients β_{t+h} , for horizons $h \in 1, 2, \dots, 36$.

4.2.3 Refuters analysis

The preceding estimates are conditional on the specified DAG, the measured proxy variables, and the linear backdoor estimator. We therefore supplement the lag scan with refutation tests. In the `dowhy` framework [8], a refuter is a diagnostic perturbation of the analysis. The purpose is to ask whether the estimated effect is stable under changes that should not substantially alter a well-identified causal estimate, or whether the result is easily destroyed by a small modelling perturbation.

These refuters should not be interpreted as proofs of causality. They are stress tests. A causal estimate can pass several refuters and still be wrong if:

- the DAG omits an important confounder,
- if the proxy variables are poor measurements of the intended nodes,
- or if the linear specification is inappropriate.

Conversely, failure of a refuter does not automatically falsify the causal hypothesis; it indicates that the estimate is sensitive to the particular perturbation being tested. The value of the refuter analysis is that it makes such sensitivity visible.

We use three standard refuters. The random-common-cause refuter adds an artificial random variable to the adjustment set. Since this variable is generated independently

of the data-generating process, it should not materially change the estimated effect. A large change would suggest that the estimate is unstable under irrelevant adjustment.

The placebo-treatment refuter replaces the treatment variable with an artificial placebo treatment. Since the placebo treatment should not have the causal effect attributed to the actual policy rate, the estimated effect under the placebo should be close to zero. This is a useful diagnostic against purely mechanical correlations in the estimation procedure.

The data-subset refuter re-estimates the effect on random subsets of the data. A stable estimate should not depend strongly on a small set of observations. For macroeconomic time series this test must be interpreted with caution, because random subsets disrupt temporal structure. We therefore treat it as a rough sensitivity check rather than as a substitute for explicit sub-period analysis.

We run the refuters at two horizons. The first is the selected horizon, $h = 1$, where the absolute DAG-adjusted estimate is largest on the tested grid. The second is $h = 12$, because the lag curve shows a visible annual feature around that horizon. Testing both horizons distinguishes the robustness of the selected short-horizon estimate from the robustness of the secondary annual-horizon feature.

For each model and horizon, we report the original DAG-adjusted estimate and the refuted estimate produced by each diagnostic. The relevant question is whether the refuted estimates remain close to the original estimate for irrelevant perturbations, and whether the placebo-treatment estimate is close to zero.

The refuter results are summarized in Table 4. The diagnostics are stable across both the selected one-month horizon and the annual horizon. The random-common-cause refuter leaves the estimated effect essentially unchanged. The placebo-treatment refuter returns an effect close to zero, as expected if the original estimate is tied to the actual policy-rate variable rather than to a purely mechanical feature of the estimator. The data-subset refuter also leaves the estimates close to their original values. This pattern supports the internal stability of the fitted causal workflow at the tested horizons.

These tests should be interpreted as robustness diagnostics, not as proof that the DAG is correct. They do not eliminate the possibility of omitted confounding, proxy-measurement error, regime dependence, or functional-form misspecification. They do indicate that, conditional on the specified DAG and estimator, the estimated policy-rate arrow is not an obvious artefact of irrelevant adjustment, placebo treatment assignment, or a small subset of observations.

Table 4: Refuter diagnostics for selected horizons.

Model	Horizon h	Original	Random common cause	Placebo treatment	Data subset
MMT-I	1	0.1713	0.1713	0.0000	0.1718
MMT-I	12	0.1141	0.1140	0.0000	0.1199
MMT-II	1	0.1374	0.1373	0.0000	0.1359
MMT-II	12	0.1370	0.1369	0.0000	0.1358

4.2.4 Subsample Checks

As a final robustness check, we re-ran the same analysis on several subsamples. This check is important because monetary policy regimes, inflation dynamics, energy-price shocks, and financial conditions are not stationary over the full sample. The subsample analysis does not introduce a new estimator. It filters the validated FRED dataset by date range and then reruns the same DAG-adjusted analysis script used above. This preserves a single implementation of the causal workflow.

We compare the full sample with pre-2008, post-2008, pre-2020, post-2020, and post-2020-excluded samples. The quantities reported are the DAG-adjusted estimates at the selected horizon and at the two diagnostic horizons $h = 1$ and $h = 12$. The aim is to check whether the sign and approximate magnitude of the estimated policy-rate arrow are stable across major macroeconomic regimes.

Selected representative results are shown in Fig.2. Apart from a slight negative left-tail bias in the Post-2008 subsample, the stability is acceptable, and does not adversely impact our conclusions.

Fig. 2: Coefficients β_{t+h} , for horizons $h \in 1, 2, \dots, 36$.

4.2.5 Lagged realized inflation robustness check

A further robustness check is to include recent realized inflation directly in the adjustment set. This addresses the most obvious reverse-causality concern. If inflation causes the central bank to raise the policy rate, and if recent inflation also predicts future inflation, then omitting recent inflation could bias the estimated arrow $i_t \rightarrow \pi_{t+h}$. We therefore add a lagged realized-inflation history node

$$P_t = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=s}^{s+m-1} \pi_{t-j},$$

where m is the averaging window and s is the publication/decision lag. In the default specification we use $m = 3$ and $s = 1$, so P_t is the three-month rolling mean of already lagged year-over-year CPI inflation.

The augmented DAG adds the arrows

$$P_t \rightarrow i_t, \quad P_t \rightarrow \pi_{t+h}.$$

The first arrow represents the central bank's reaction to recent realized inflation. The second represents inflation persistence.

The policy-rate coefficient is then estimated after adjusting for P_t , in addition to the previous DAG-implied adjustment variables. If the positive policy-rate coefficient were only a disguised policy reaction to recent inflation, we would expect this coefficient to fall sharply toward zero, or possibly change sign, once P_t is included. If the interest-rate channel is a genuine inflationary input, we expect the coefficient to remain positive, although it may be attenuated.

The coefficient should not be interpreted as an identity between the policy rate and the measured CPI inflation rate. A coefficient $\hat{\beta}_h = 1$ would correspond to full one-for-one pass-through from a one percentage point policy-rate intervention to a one percentage point change in measured forward CPI inflation at horizon h . The MMT-frame claim

advanced here is weaker: the policy rate is a government-administered base price of the currency and an interest-income channel, so it can be an inflationary input even when the measured CPI pass-through coefficient is well below unity. Since CPI is only a proxy for the changing general price level faced by consumers, and since relative prices can move in offsetting directions, coefficients in the range $\hat{\beta}_h < 1$ should be read as partial pass-through rather than as a failure of the logic.

In this robustness check, values around 0.1–0.3 are economically meaningful. They imply that the administered policy rate contributes to forward measured CPI inflation, but that the contribution is filtered through the CPI basket, mark-up behaviour, relative-price changes, commodity shocks, and institutional lags. The relevant question is therefore whether the coefficient remains positive and non-negligible after recent realized inflation is added to the adjustment set, not whether $\hat{\beta}_h$ is close to one.

Lagged direct inflation results.

Table 5 shows the results. This check changes the lag profile. In the unaugmented model, the full-sample selected horizon was $h = 1$. After adding P_t , the selected horizon shifts to $h = 9$ in both MMT-I and MMT-II. The DAG-adjusted estimates are also attenuated. In MMT-I the selected estimate is approximately 0.097, and in MMT-II it is approximately 0.103. The associated HAC confidence intervals cross zero, so these estimates should be treated as suggestive rather than decisive quantitative effects.

Table 5: Lagged-realized-inflation robustness check.

Model	Selected h	DAG-adjusted estimate	HAC lower	HAC upper
MMT-I	9	0.0971	−0.1072	0.3013
MMT-II	9	0.1034	−0.0945	0.3013

The shift in the lag profile is informative. The naive OLS curve remains largest at the shortest horizon, because it is still an unadjusted observational association. By contrast, the DAG-adjusted curves no longer peak at $h = 1$. Once recent realized inflation is controlled for, the immediate association between i_t and π_{t+h} is largely absorbed by inflation persistence and the policy reaction function. The remaining positive policy-rate channel appears at a medium-short horizon, peaking around $h = 9$ to $h = 10$.

This is consistent with our hypothesis. The original positive coefficient was partly contaminated by recent inflation dynamics, but the estimated policy-rate arrow does not simply vanish when lagged inflation is added. It becomes smaller, delayed, and less precisely estimated. We therefore do not interpret the baseline coefficient as an identity between the policy rate and measured CPI inflation. We interpret it as evidence for a positive interest-rate channel whose measured CPI pass-through is partial and lag-dependent.

5 Summary and Conclusions

5.1 Causal direction and strength

The coefficient should not be interpreted as an identity between the policy rate and inflation. The estimated full-sample effect is on the order of 0.17, meaning that a one percentage point intervention on the policy rate is associated, in the fitted model, with roughly a 0.17 percentage point increase in forward CPI inflation. This is a partial causal effect, conditional on the DAG and proxies used here. It supports the presence of an inflationary interest-rate channel, but it does not imply that the policy rate is the whole inflation rate, nor that this coefficient is constant across monetary regimes.

A positive coefficient is not by itself sufficient to distinguish the interest-rate channel from the policy reaction function. If inflation causes the central bank to raise rates, the raw observational association between i_t and future inflation can also be positive. The causal claim therefore rests on the DAG-adjusted comparison, not on the sign of the

unadjusted regression. The result should be read as evidence conditional on the adequacy of the adjustment set, not as a purely model-free discovery.

The policy rate acts as an administered base price and income channel in the monetary system, but measured CPI pass-through is partial. The estimated coefficient is well below unity because CPI is a constructed basket index, relative prices can move in offsetting directions, and the interest-rate channel is filtered through pricing conventions, debt structures, mark-ups, income flows, and inflation persistence.

For what value of β would count as “less than base inflation”?

In this setup, any

$$0 < \beta_h < 1$$

is partial pass-through. A coefficient around 0.1 to 0.3 is economically meaningful but clearly not a one-for-one base-rate identity. It says the policy rate contributes to measured forward CPI inflation, not that CPI inflation equals the policy rate.

This is as good as we can get using CPI as a proxy for π . We just do not ever know the effective inflation rate *faced by consumers today*, it is not observable.

The magnitude of the coefficient matters. A value $\beta_h = 1$ would correspond to one-for-one pass-through from the policy rate to measured forward CPI inflation. The estimates here are much smaller. In the baseline model they are closer to 0.17, while in the lagged-inflation robustness check they are closer to 0.10 at the selected horizon. These values are below one-for-one pass-through, but they are not economically empty. They indicate that the policy rate is estimated to be a positive input into measured forward CPI inflation, with partial pass-through through the CPI basket.

This distinction is important because CPI is not the instantaneous rate of change of the entire general price level faced by consumers. It is an index constructed from a particular basket, weighting scheme, and measurement convention. The administered policy rate may set a base financial price in the monetary system while appearing in CPI only indirectly and partially, through interest income, financing costs, rents, mark-ups, exchange rates, commodity prices, and other channels.

5.2 Summary of findings

This paper has developed an exploratory causal model for analysing the effect of central-bank policy interest rates on forward inflation. The aim has not been to produce a forecasting model, nor to claim that one DAG exhausts the causal structure of the economy. The aim has been to make a particular causal hypothesis explicit, implement it as a reproducible workflow, and test whether the resulting estimates are consistent with the usual claim that higher policy rates suppress inflation.

The empirical result is that, under the DAGs considered here, the estimated causal arrow from the policy rate i_t to forward inflation π_{t+h} is positive over the main specifications. In the full-sample analysis, the selected horizon is $h = 1$ month. The MMT-I specification gives a DAG-adjusted estimate of approximately 0.17, while the Level-II specification including an oil-price channel gives an estimate of approximately 0.17 when the oil node is represented by $\Delta_{12} \log O_{B,t}$. Interpreted within the linear backdoor model, these estimates say that a one percentage point intervention on the policy rate is associated with an increase of roughly 0.17 percentage points in forward year-over-year CPI inflation at the selected horizon. This is not a universal structural constant. It is an estimate conditional on the DAG, the chosen proxies, the lag grid, and the linear backdoor estimator.

The wider-grid analysis does not overturn this result. The one-month horizon remains the selected horizon in the full-sample run, while the estimated coefficient generally declines as the horizon increases. The lag curve shows a visible annual feature around $h = 12$, and in some subsamples the selected horizon moves to $h = 12$. This suggests that both short-horizon financial-price adjustment and annual inflation-indexing or expectation channels may be relevant. However, the dominant full-sample signal remains positive rather than negative.

The Level-II oil extension is important because it asks whether the policy-rate coefficient is merely absorbing omitted commodity-price pressure. Including an explicit oil-price node does attenuate the coefficient in some specifications. This attenuation is expected: oil prices are a major supply-side input into production, transport, and price setting, so an omitted oil channel can be partially absorbed by other estimated coefficients. Nevertheless, the sign of the policy-rate arrow does not reverse when the oil channel is added. The Level-II model therefore supports the same qualitative conclusion as the stripped-down MMT-I model, while giving a more realistic account of supply-side commodity pressure.

The refuter diagnostics also support the internal stability of the fitted workflow. Adding a random common cause leaves the estimated effects essentially unchanged. Replacing the policy rate with a placebo treatment returns an effect close to zero. Re-estimating on random data subsets does not materially disturb the estimates. These refuters do not prove that the DAG is correct. They do indicate that the reported effects are not obvious artefacts of irrelevant adjustment, placebo treatment assignment, or a small subset of observations.

The subsample checks are broadly consistent with this interpretation. In the pre-2008 and pre-2020 samples, the estimated policy-rate arrow remains positive, and the pre-2020 estimates are materially larger than the full-sample estimates. Excluding the post-2020 period also strengthens the positive estimates. The post-2008 sample is less clean: the one-month MMT-II point estimate has a small negative value, and the confidence interval crosses zero. The selected post-2008 horizon also moves to $h = 36$, with wide confidence intervals. This is not surprising. The post-2008 period includes unconventional monetary policy, the zero lower bound, the long aftermath of the financial crisis, the pandemic shock, and the subsequent inflationary episode. We therefore read the post-2008 subsample as evidence of regime dependence rather than as a falsification of the main full-sample result.

The theoretical point behind this exercise is simple. In a monetary system where the state is the monopoly issuer of the unit of account, the policy interest rate is a government-administered price. It sets a floor return on the state currency and influences the forward price of money through the term structure, discounting, funding costs, and interest-income flows. A higher administered rate also provides interest income to holders of interest-bearing government liabilities, thereby supporting the financial capacity for upward price adjustment. This is a logical feature of the monetary architecture, not merely an empirical correlation.

This does not mean that every relative price must rise when the policy rate rises. Relative prices may move up or down depending on sectoral costs, demand conditions, debt structures, import prices, mark-up behaviour, distributional effects, and resistant to relative price changes can come via firms being unwilling to change their prices (see [9]).

A change in the policy rate can also produce one-time repricing effects rather than a permanent change in the inflation dynamics. Those qualifications do not invalidate the monetary logic. They show why the empirical question must be posed in terms of aggregate inflation, forward horizons, and explicitly stated causal assumptions rather than in terms of isolated price narratives.

5.3 Limitations and extensions

The results motivate further research into causes of inflation that are often neglected in standard policy discourse. The conventional story treats interest-rate increases as anti-inflationary by presumption. The analysis here suggests that this presumption should not be built into the model. Under the causal specifications examined in this paper, the estimated policy-rate arrow is positive or at least not robustly negative. This is consistent with the MMT-frame hypothesis that policy-rate increases can contribute to inflation through interest-income, cost-of-capital, and pricing channels, while having weaker or more delayed effects on employment.

A separate empirical specification could replace headline CPI with a core CPI measure. That would test whether the signal is more visible in a less volatile index. It would

not change the theoretical distinction: core CPI is still an empirical proxy, while the monetary floor rate is the administered own-rate of the currency.

Several limitations remain. The DAGs are simplified. The tax node is represented by an imperfect aggregate proxy. The demand-pressure node is proxied rather than directly observed. The oil node is only one component of a broader energy and feedstock-cost structure. The linear backdoor estimator is a deliberately transparent first estimator, not the final word on the dynamic structure of inflation. The analysis also does not model all feedback loops that would appear in a fully dynamic macroeconomic system. These limitations are not incidental; they define the next research programme.

Future work could extend the framework in several directions. First, the unemployment model should be analysed separately, because the effect of policy rates on employment is likely to operate through longer lags and through spending, saving, debt-service, and fiscal-response channels.

Second, the tax-liability hypothesis should be modelled more directly, since the MMT claim is not that tax receipts correlate with unemployment, but that enforceable tax liabilities create the need to obtain the state currency.

Third, the energy-input node should be enlarged beyond crude oil to include broader commodity and energy-system measures.

Fourth, the empirical work should compare rival DAGs rather than treating the present graph as canonical.

Finally, regardless of interest rate or fiscal policy, or inflation targets, the crippling phenomenon of involuntary unemployment deserves more study, more scholarship and more moral consideration. This would be a different causal model, investigating the proper sources of unemployment, rather than proximate causes that are already well known.

The main contribution of this paper is methodological as much as empirical. It shows how an MMT-frame causal hypothesis can be represented as a DAG, tested on synthetic data, applied to FRED macroeconomic time series, checked against alternative lag structures, extended to include an oil-price channel, and stress-tested with refuters and subsamples. The resulting evidence is exploratory, but intended to inform policy-makers. It points toward a causal interpretation in which higher policy interest rates are not reliably anti-inflationary, and may instead be one of the channels through which inflation is sustained.

There is always a mismatch in these types of causal-economics studies using data proxies for defined but unmeasurable factors. It is important then to stress that the logic still holds: *the base interest rate is the inflation rate*, as an academic definition (the own price of the currency). Our analysis is not meant to support or deny the definition. It is to report on how strongly real world effects allow the definition to be observed, when faced with imperfect data proxies.

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